

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of *N*-[α -(Phenoxy/ Substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/propionyl]piperazines/ morpholines

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Piperazines and morpholines are very useful in the field of medicine¹. Phenoxyacetic and propionic acids and their derivatives also possess a wide spectrum of biological activities². These results prompted us to undertake the synthesis of *N*- α -aryloxy-alkanoyl-piperazines/morpholines (Scheme 1).

In antimicrobial testing, compounds **1a**, **b**, **e-h**, **k**, **r**, **s**, **v**, and **2b**, **c** and **e** showed good activity against the specific bacteria (zone of inhibition, 9–16 mm) and fungi (zone of inhibition, 48–78 mm, while other compounds exhibited mild to moderate activity. In anti-inflammatory screening), the chloro series compounds **2b**, **c** and **e** were found to show significant activity (% inhibition: 42, 33 and 36 respectively) as compared to the standard drug phenylbutazone (45% inhibition).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a melting apparatus and are uncorrected. The purity of com-

pounds was checked by tlc. Structures of the compounds were established by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The title compounds showed characteristic ir bands at 2 900, 1 485, 1 470 (CH₂), 2 900, 1450, 1 370 (C-CH₃), 1 600–1 610 (CO-N), 1 240, 1 010 (-C-C-C-), 1 120 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 2 950, 1 340 (secondary NH) and 1 680, 1 140, 860, 750 cm⁻¹ (substitution in aromatic ring).

The title compounds were synthesised as described below. To a solution of aryloxyacetic/aryloxy propionic acids (0.05–0.06 mol), prepared by condensing the sodium salt of the appropriate phenols with chloroacetic acid or α -chloropropionic acid in EtOAc (50 ml) was added thionyl chloride (0.06–0.07 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for ~8 h. The acid chlorides thus obtained were added dropwise to an ice-cold mixture of aqueous NaOH (5 ml; 4*N* NaOH) and piperazine/morpholine (0.037 mol) with stirring for 45–60 min. The separated amides were filtered and

purified over a column of silica gel using petroleum ether-benzene or CHCl_3 -EtOAc mixture as eluant and crystallised from $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6/\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$.

Biological activities: The compounds were tested for antifungal activity by filter paper disc method³ against *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium crysogenum*, *Trychophyton mentagrophytes* and *Candida albicans* at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. Antibacterial activity was tested³ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi* at 25 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. Anti-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2*

Compd. no.	R	X	M.p. °C
1a	H	H	59-60
b	H	2,4,6-Br	100-102
c	CH_3	2,4,6-Br	88-90
d	H	2,4-Br	110-112
e	H	2,4,6-Cl	80-83
f	CH_3	2,4,6-Cl	96-98
g	H	2,4-Cl	115-116
h	CH_3	2,4-Cl	98-100
i	H	2-Cl	59-60
j	CH_3	2-Cl	56-57
k	H	4-Cl	33-34
l	CH_3	4-Cl	38-40
m	H	2- CH_3	80-82
n	CH_3	2- CH_3	40-42
o	H	3- CH_3	75-76
p	CH_3	3- CH_3	79-80
q	H	4- CH_3	149-150
r	CH_3	4- CH_3	70-72
s	H	2,4,6- NO_2	89-90
t	H	2- NO_2	260-262
u	H	3- NO_2	190-192
v	H	4- NO_2	105-107
2a	CH_3	2,4,6-Br	90-92
b	CH_3	2,4,6-Cl	48-50
c	CH_3	2,4-Cl	96-98
d	CH_3	2-Cl	55-56
e	CH_3	4-Cl	49-50
f	H	2- CH_3	96-100
g	CH_3	CH_3	80-82
h	H	3- CH_3	101-103
i	CH_3	3- CH_3	76-77
j	H	4- CH_3	130-132
k	CH_3	4- CH_3	68-70

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

inflammatory activity was evaluated by carrageenin induced rat paw oedema method⁴.

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